

Attitude of Youth towards Mobile Advertising in Higher Education

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study is to investigate attitude of the youth towards the mobile advertising or m-advertising. The result of the research on the basis of demographics shows that the youth experienced most of the ads in the form of text & banner ads, rewarded ads, and in-app ads but they prefer ads in the form of playable ads, rewarded ads, and rich media ads. The most of the m-advertising experienced is on the internet browsers and social networks. To find the attitude of youth we have used the correlation and multiple regression analysis in our study.

Keywords:- Attitude, variable affecting attitude, youth, mobile advertising, m-advertising, multiple regression analysis, reliability analysis, Cronbach's alpha.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern communication technologies directly impact the tools and techniques used in marketing. Rapid advancements in mobile communication have created new channels for marketers to connect with their target audiences. Multipurpose means of communication by receiving and sending text messages, graphics, data, music, video etc. These stated features of mobile phones make mobile phones one of the most important means of communication.

Mobile devices are direct marketing tools that allow for constant contact with target audiences wherever they are and whenever they choose to be [5]. Accessibility, frequency, and speed of mobile advertising communication are raised based on consumer information speed is accelerated.

791 4G networks were commercially active in 240 nations as of January 2022, according to data gathered from the Global Mobile Suppliers Association. The same research states once more that there are 4 billion 916 million mobile communication subscribers worldwide. Compared to 1.14 billion in 2004, this amount was 3.3 billion in 2007. According to the Institute of Information Technologies and Communication (BTK), as of August 2022 there were 1.15 billion mobile subscribers and 1 billion mobile phones in India. When at the end of 2010, there were 7.8 billion mobile subscribers, up from 2.7 billion in 2005.

Mobile advertising has become a significant communication channel and enabled the quick adoption of wireless technology in marketing strategies along with the rapid increase in mobile phone ownership and use. The following reasons can be used to explain why mobile phones have grown in importance in marketing: customers

can use their mobile phones at any time and anywhere, they are always available for communication, one-on-one communication garners more attention, messages can be responded to later by recording them, there is a possibility for one-to-one audiovisual communication, and mobile phones offer suitability for customers and efficiency for marketing managers. Social Media Advertising, in particular, has achieved great success in this area.

Since it can tailor messaging and is interactive, marketers are placing an ever-increasing emphasis on it.

This study's direction was determined in part by the rapid growth of social media advertising and its prominence among promotional tactics. As with any newly implemented application, Social media advertising requires that strategies be tailored to the reactions and expectations of the target audience.

To make better use of this promotional tool, it will be useful to understand consumer attitudes and opinions. Social media advertising reaches large audiences.

Users have a variety of traits and expectations, as is well recognized. Therefore, marketing campaigns will be more target-specific when these distinctions are taken into account. In this direction, the study sought to ascertain whether views about mobile advertising differed between young people and adults. As is well known, the consumption patterns and styles of youth and adults are very different from one another. The differences can be seen in a number of areas, including media preferences, universities, brands, and advertising messages. The study's objective was to find out how young people felt about mobile advertising and whether there were any differences in how they accepted or rejected a university/college.

Mobile advertising has been considered a new form of marketing or advertising and provided new opportunities for companies to do businesses. Marketing activities conducted via mobile devices enable advertisers to directly communicate with potential target customers (i.e., youth in our case) in a fast speed and regardless of the geographical location. Mobile advertising has been recently referred to as one of the best means to cut through the clutter and interact directly with the target consumer. Hence, with the trend toward direct, one-to-one marketing, more attention is being paid to the use of the mobile channel as a means of effectively advertising to target consumers. Indian mobile market is one of the fastest growing markets due to the increase in the number of middle-income consumers and is forecasted to reach billions of users in the next decade. Thus, research on mobile advertising would impact greatly on the way business is done.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Therefore, research on mobile advertising would have a significant impact on how business is conducted.

A cell phone is one of the few untouchable private areas that many people still have, allowing them to connect and socialize while yet maintaining control over how they use it. In this sense, when creating a marketing strategy, marketers should consider the needs of consumers for security and privacy.

In order to achieve their marketing plan's goals, marketers must strike a balance between involving consumers in their marketing mix and doing so. The marketers must comprehend the elements that influence target customer acceptance of mobile phone commercials, such as incentives and consumer attitudes, in order to accomplish this goal.

In India, there were 1.5 billion mobile customers as of December 2021, and the mobile penetration rate was almost 60.63%, according to the Telecom Regulatory Authority of India. Around \$84 billion in US dollars was the anticipated worth of e-commerce in India in 2021. In which just mobile devices accounted for over 67% of the total sales.

These facts demonstrate how much money is made from the use and selling of mobile phones; hence it is crucial that mobile businesses perform research.

This study explores consumer perceptions of mobile advertising applications that have recently launched or are soon to do so in India, as businesses increasingly recognize the value of mobile advertising and invest in creating and implementing mobile marketing applications. This study's direction was determined in part by the rapid growth of social media advertising and its prominence among promotional tactics. As with any newly implemented application, social media advertising requires that strategies be tailored to the reactions and expectations of the target audience.

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In study on marketing and information systems, attitude is a key term. According to Fishbein, a person's attitude is "a taught tendency." A person "would respond to an object (or an idea) or a number of things (or viewpoints)" based on this propensity. According to Kotler, "a person's persisting positive or negative judgements, emotional sensations, and action patterns toward an object or concept" constitute their attitude. There is a substantial amount of literature on consumer attitudes about advertising in general and especially advertising through mobile since scholars have been researching the topic for a very long time. Another crucial element for information systems research is attitude. For instance, the technology acceptance model that forecasts the usage of information systems includes five main constructs: attitude, use, perceived utility, and perceived ease of use. Several research have examined and supported the links between attitude, intention, and behaviour.

The terms "wireless marketing" and "mobile marketing target audience through wireless technology. According to Carter (2008), mobile marketing is "the systematic planning, implementation, and control of a variety of commercial operations intended to bring customers and sellers together for the purpose of facilitating the exchange or transfer of products at a mutually advantageous price" (p. 62). Their mobile phones serve as the primary point of communication with the intended customers in this situation.

Balasubramanian, Peterson, and Jarvenpaa (2002) wrote about the effects of mobile technology on mobile commerce (m-commerce), describing it as a form of communication that involves "either one-way or interactive, between two or more humans, between a human (or humans) and one or more inanimate objects, or between a human (or humans) and two or more inanimate objects (e.g., between devices)" (p. 350). These writers discussed a conceived framework for mobile technologies and m-commerce using time and space notions. They clarified that a consumer who doesn't know where the store is or who finds it difficult to get around because of distance, time restraints, or other obstacles may be deterred from purchasing goods and services from a physical and mortar retail store. Although, it is if the merchant offers such mobile apps phone (Balasubramanian et al., 2002; Altuna and Konuk, 2009), to buy such a good or service via his/her mobile. Although some marketing activities are not accessible via mobile technologies, consumers who live in a world without mobile technology view location and time as limitations.

Customized information is another unique characteristic that makes mobile marketing (m-marketing) stand out as a significant and cutting-edge marketing instrument, in addition to closing the gap created by time, distance, convenience, free transportation, and interactive channels of contact (Friedrich et al. 2009).. Many marketers are prepared to invest in m-marketing, according to a poll done by Airwide Solutions (a provider of mobile

infrastructure and application services). 50 multinational businesses participated in this poll, and the results showed that more companies are planning to allocate a larger amount of their future marketing budgets to mobile initiatives. 71% of those surveyed said they would spend up to 10% of their budget on mobile marketing (Thurner, 2008; Altuna and Konuk, 2009).

According to research, mobile marketing may be combined with traditional marketing tools to promote the goods and services of companies, which will increase the efficacy and efficiency of the whole marketing strategy. For the following reason, mobile devices have been regarded as one of the best means of disseminating marketing information. In addition to being affordable and making it simple to reach the desired consumer category, the majority of customers carry their mobile phones almost constantly (Thurner, 2008; Altuna and Konuk, 2009).

A. Mobile Marketing and Advertising

A good potential for wireless Internet applications, including wireless marketing and advertising, has been generated by the increased adoption of mobile phones in recent years as an extension of the Internet environment. Using wireless devices like mobile phones, wireless Internet services enable interactive access to Internet-based applications and data. Wireless marketing is defined by the Wireless Advertising Association (WAA) as the transmission of commercial messages to mobile devices like smartphones through a wireless network. Numerous service providers, such as cellular carriers, fixed and mobile portals, wireless application service providers, device makers, consumer brands, and mobile virtual network operators, can provide wireless Internet service. Wireless marketing is a very promising direct marketing

medium that benefits from the Web's interactive and rapid response features.

Internet advertising enables the identification of specific consumers and the analysis of their behaviour. The mobility restriction associated with fixed-line Internet connection is eased by mobile advertising. For location- and time-sensitive events, it is reasonable to assume that mobile advertising will benefit customers more. Mobile advertising has to be more individualised and may take various forms because a person can essentially be accessible at any time, anywhere using a mobile phone.

B. Attitudes towards mobile advertising

According to Mehta and Purvis (1996), attitudes regarding an advertisement are "a learnt inclination to respond in a consistently favourable or unfavourable manner toward advertising in general." In this instance, it is crucial to keep in mind that attitudes toward mobile advertising pertain to consumer perceptions of this form of advertising generally. It doesn't discuss how customers feel about a certain commercial. Generally speaking, attitudes are mental states that people utilise to determine how they perceive their external world and how they react to it (Aaker, Kumar, and Day, 1995)

Our research has so concentrated on the factors that influence consumers' perceptions of mobile advertising in general. In this study, multiple factors have been used to gauge consumer views regarding mobile device advertising.

The various parts of the framework are shown in Figure 1 for further explanation, with the dependent variable "attitude toward advertising via mobile devices."

Fig. 1: Antecedents of Attitude towards Advertising via Mobile Devices

III. OBJECTIVES

This study aims:

- To find out the attitude of youth towards M-Advertising in Higher Education
- To find out attitude on the basis of Demographic
- To ascertain the association of gender with the attitude towards higher education
- Impact of M-advertising on Youth
- Attitude association of demographic (gender age)
- To find out the attitude of youth towards different types of m-advertising

IV. METHODOLOGY

The study primarily aims to comprehend youth views toward mobile advertisements and their underlying behavioural intentions meaning deduced from the obtained data serves as the foundation for the quantitative data, and analysis is carried out using diagrams and statistics. It stands in stark contrast to the qualitative data, which places a strong emphasis on conceptualization and comprehension.

The study is based on primary data because it couldn't be completed using secondary data alone. The psychological process that mediates the observable links between attitudes and behaviour is described by the model using each

individual's beliefs, attitudes, intentions, and behaviour. Intention then has an impact on their actual ad-receiving

behaviour.

Fig. 2: Conceptual Framework

From the structure mentioned above, five sets of hypotheses may be created :

Hypothesis 1: There is a relationship between Entertainment and Youth’s Attitude towards M-Advertising

Hypothesis 2: There is a relationship between Informativeness and Youth’s Attitude towards M-Advertising.

Hypothesis 3: There is a relationship between Credibility and Youth’s Attitude towards M-Advertising.

Hypothesis 4: There is a relationship between Irritation and Youth’s Attitude towards M-Advertising.

Hypothesis 5: There is a relationship between Personalization and Youth’s Attitude towards M-Advertising.

V. DATA COLLECTION

Primary data and secondary data were both gathered for the study. The secondary data gathered includes a study of previous research on the subject from various studies, consumer perceptions of commercials, and their responses to them. The survey's constructed questionnaire, which included data on the respondents' demographics, traits, and behaviour intentions, was used to gather the survey's primary data.

Structured surveying is the approach used to gather data, and it entails I creating the survey instrument (questionnaire) and (ii) disseminating it to potential participants.

VI. RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

• **Sampling**

Considering the accessibility and availability of the respondents, convenient samples have been utilised to choose the samples. To prevent gender inequality, both male and female volunteers have been chosen.

VII. DATA FINDINGS & ANALYSIS

A. *Profile of Youths*

In total, 276 questionnaires were collected, with all being coming from an internet-based survey. We included questions about respondents' gender, age, education, and their interaction with M-advertising, such as their experience and exposure to mobile advertising, in our questionnaire. Our sample contains 75.7% males and 24.3% females, as shown in Table 1.

Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	209	75.7	75.7	75.7
	Female	67	24.3	24.3	100.0
Total		276	100.0	100.0	

Table 1: Gender spread in our sample

Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	15-18	90	32.6	32.6	32.6
	19-22	86	31.2	31.2	63.8
	23-25	100	36.2	36.2	100.0
	Total	276	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Age spread in our sample

Marketers and advertisers can benefit from investigating respondents' technical smart phone capabilities, habits, and experience with smart phone advertising. These findings provide an overview of the most common mobile advertising communication channels, respondents' willingness to receive advertising messages, the format of a preferred advertising message, and overall customer attitudes toward mobile advertising. As suggested by, both marketers and advertisers can use those data to their and consumers' mutual benefit (Ducoffe, 1995).

We asked respondents which form and channel they had the most experience with mobile advertising through because we believe it is important for advertisers to know which forms and channels have been used and to what extent. Knowing this provides advertisers with valuable information about the visibility of their advertising messages and, as a result, reveals the so-called window of opportunity in terms of unexploited mobile advertising forms and channels (see tables 3 and 4).

Which form of Mobile-advertising have you experienced the most?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	In-app Ads	39	14.1	14.1	14.1
	Interstitial Ads	35	12.7	12.7	26.8
	Native Ads	29	10.5	10.5	37.3
	Playable Ads	27	9.8	9.8	47.1
	Rewarded Ads	40	14.5	14.5	61.6
	Rich Media Ads	31	11.2	11.2	72.8
	Text & Banner Ads	48	17.4	17.4	90.2
	Video Ads	27	9.8	9.8	100.0
	Total	276	100.0	100.0	

Table 3: Most Common M-advertising form

Where did you experience Mobile-Advertising the most?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Apps	48	17.4	17.4	17.4
	E-mail	56	20.3	20.3	37.7
	Games	45	16.3	16.3	54.0
	Internet Browsers	72	26.1	26.1	80.1
	Social Networks	55	19.9	19.9	100.0
	Total	276	100.0	100.0	

Table 4: Spread of M-advertising channels in our sample.

The item pertaining to youths' preferred mobile advertising forms was included in order to provide useful information to both marketers and advertisers when planning advertising campaigns or promotional events. This item reflects on how customers expect to be contacted or see

advertising messages. As we can see from reviewing literature, soliciting customer feedback increases positive attitude and credibility toward the advertising message and advertiser (see table 5) Ducoffe (1995), MacKenzie (1989).

Which form of Mobile-advertising are you willing to accept the most?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	In-app Ads	31	11.2	11.2	11.2
	Interstitial Ads	29	10.5	10.5	21.7
	Native Ads	38	13.8	13.8	35.5
	Playable Ads	47	17.0	17.0	52.5
	Rewarded Ads	40	14.5	14.5	67.0
	Rich Media Ads	39	14.1	14.1	81.2
	Text & Banner Ads	23	8.3	8.3	89.5
	Video Ads	29	10.5	10.5	100.0
	Total	276	100.0	100.0	

Table 5: Youths' preferred form of M-advertising

serves as an indicator of annoyance and, once again, can be valued by advertisers as feedback on mobile marketing strategies. They can see how customers are

exposed to mobile advertising messages and decide whether to increase, balance, or decrease their advertising (see Table 6).

How often do you view and read mobile advertisements?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-5 per day	91	33.0	33.0	33.0
	5-10 per day	89	32.2	32.2	65.2
	More than 10 per day	96	34.8	34.8	100.0
	Total	276	100.0	100.0	

Table 6: Frequency of exposure of Youths’ to M-advertising

B. Reliability Analysis

Reliability of the questionnaire was tested using Cronbach’s Alpha Analysis.

According to Tavakol and Dennick (2011), a reliability test was used to ensure that results were generated using measurements that could be measured consistently.

Cronbach's Alpha is a measure of reliability. Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficients are normally between 0 and 1. George and Mallery (2003) recommended that the acceptance level of reliability be greater than 0.70. Table 7 shows the results from Reliability analysis done using Cronbach’s Alpha.

Variables	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Entertainment	4	0.880
Informativeness	4	0.876
Credibility	4	0.943
Irritation	4	0.975
Personalization	4	0.827
Attitude	6	0.994

Table 7: Reliability Statistics

Tables 7 show the results of the reliability test derived from the pilot test, with the overall samples. Cronbach's Alpha values range from 0.827 to 0.994. Attitude has the highest value of 0.994. Cronbach's Alpha of all the variables

are all greater than 0.70, indicating that the measurement scales are reliable. As a result, in this study, all independent variables are capable of producing consistent results (George & Mallery, 2003).

Descriptive Statistics

	N Statistic	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic
Entertainment	276	3.8850	1.78940
Informativeness	276	2.9158	1.51265
Credibility	276	2.4158	1.19141
Irritation	276	4.2364	1.52018
Personalization	276	4.3850	0.79923
Attitude	276	4.0260	1.40685
Valid N (listwise)	276		

Constructs Central Tendencies Measurement

Table 8: Central Tendencies of Constructs

The mean of the sample ranges from 2.4158 to 4.2364 while the standard deviation ranges from 0.79923 to 1.78940.

With a mean of 3.8850 and a standard deviation of 1.78940, majority of Youth neither agree nor disagree that M-advertising is entertaining. Furthermore, informativeness yields a mean of 2.9158 and a standard deviation of 1.51265. Youths slightly disagree that M-advertising provides them with reliable and timely information. The mean of credibility of 2.4158 and standard deviation of 1.19141 indicate that respondents disagree that M-advertisement is credible and trustworthy. Then, irritation with a mean of 4.2364 and a standard deviation of 1.52018 indicates that respondents agree that M-advertisements gives a sensation of irritation and annoy a lot. Following that,

personalization with a mean of 4.3850 and a standard deviation of 0.79923 demonstrates that M-advertisements are tailored according to theyouth’s requirement but are not specified. Finally, youths' attitudes toward M-advertising are positive, with a mean of 4.0260 and a standard deviation of 1.40685.

C. Correlation Analysis

Pearson correlation analysis is used to investigate the relationship between the variables (Wong and Hiew, 2005). According to Field (2013), the correlation coefficient value should not be greater than 0.80 to avoid multicollinearity. There is no multicollinearity because the highest correlation coefficient is 0.749. At $p < 0.01$, all variables were found to be statistically significant (Table 9).

Correlations

		Entertainment	Informativeness	Credibility	Irritation	Personalization	Attitude
Attitude	Pearson Correlation	0.745	0.634	0.664	-0.942	0.749	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	
	N	276	276	276	276	276	276

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 9: Correlation between the Constructs

D. Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression is used to test the value of a dependent variable with more than one independent variable (Malhorta & Peterson, 2006). Multiple linear regressions are

a data analysis technique used to determine the strength of the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.898 ^a	0.896	0.896	0.08280

a. Predictors: (Constant), Personalization, Credibility, Entertainment, Irritation, Informativeness

Table 10: Model Summary

Model		Coefficients ^a							
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	2.272	0.22			10.32	<0.0001	1.839	2.705
	Entertainment	0.06	0.012	0.076		4.917	<0.0001	0.036	0.084
	Informativeness	-0.206	0.046	-0.222		-4.508	<0.0001	-0.297	-0.116
	Credibility	0.092	0.027	0.078		3.371	0.001	0.038	0.146
	Irritation	-0.539	0.03	-0.583		-17.691	<0.0001	-0.599	-0.479
	Personalization	0.954	0.014	0.542		67.678	<0.0001	0.926	0.982

a. Dependent Variable: Attitude

Table 11: Regression Analysis

According to the R-square value of 0.898, entertainment, informativeness, irritation, credibility, and personalization accounted for 89.8% of consumer attitudes toward m-advertising. To put it another way, the five independent variables explained 89.8% of the consumer attitude toward mobile advertising. Other factors not

considered in this study would explain the remaining 10.2% of consumer attitudes toward m-advertising.

Youth attitudes toward M-advertising are strongly associated with Entertainment (p<0.0001), Informativeness (p<0.0001), Credibility (p=0.001), Irritation (p<0.0001), and Personalization (p<0.0001).

Hypotheses	Pearson Correlation	Multiple Linear Regression			
	Result	Statistic	Beta	p-value	Hypotheses
H1: There is a positive relationship between Entertainment and Youth's Attitude towards M-Advertising.	0.745	0.06	0.076	<0.0001	Accepted
H2: There is a positive relationship between Informativeness and Youth's Attitude towards M-Advertising.	0.634	-0.206	-0.222	<0.0001	Accepted
H3: There is a positive relationship between Credibility and Youth's Attitude towards M-Advertising.	0.664	0.092	0.078	0.001	Accepted
H4: There is a positive relationship between Irritation and Youth's Attitude towards M-Advertising.	-0.942	-0.539	-0.583	<0.0001	Accepted
H5: There is a positive relationship between Personalization and Youth's Attitude towards M-Advertising.	0.749	0.954	0.542	<0.0001	Accepted

Table 12: Findings Personalization is found to be the most important determinant, with Irritation being the least important.

The model summation adopted can be derived based on:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 EN + \beta_2 IN + \beta_3 CR + \beta_4 IR + \beta_5 PE$$

Where Y = Youth Attitude towards M-Advertising,

X1 = Entertainment (EN)

X2 = Informativeness (IN)

X3 = Credibility (CR)

X4 = Irritation (IR)

X5 = Personalization (PE)

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 EN + \beta_2 IN + \beta_3 CR + \beta_4 IR + \beta_5 PE$$

$$Y = (2.272) + (0.060)*EN + (-0.206)*IN + (0.092)*CR + (-0.539)*IR + (0.954)*PE$$

This equation demonstrates that Youth's Attitude toward Mobile-Advertising are positively related to Entertainment, Credibility, and Personalization. While Youth's Attitude toward Mobile-Advertising were found to be inversely related to Informativeness and Irritation.

VIII. FINDINGS

This study is aimed to find the Attitude of Youths towards M-advertising or Mobile-advertising.

The results of the analysis of the study shows that there is a significant positive relationship between Youths attitude towards Mobile-advertising and the factors taken into consideration to conduct the study, i.e., Entertainment, Informativeness, Credibility, Irritation, and Personalization.

In total there are 5 different factors that helps us to find the Youths Attitude towards Mobile-Advertising. Out of these 5 factors, four are positively correlated with the Youths Attitude towards Mobile-Advertising while one of the factor is negatively correlated with it. The positively correlated factors are Entertainment, Informativeness, Credibility, and Personalization. And the negatively correlated factor is Irritation. So, it can be said that all the hypotheses of the study are supported.

The Regression analysis shows that different factors have different impact on the overall compliment of the Youths attitude towards Mobile-Advertising. Out of five factors, three have positive impact (Entertainment, Credibility, and Personalization) while the other two have negative impact (Informativeness and Irritation). The most positive impact on Youths attitude towards Mobile-Advertising is by Personalization having a impact factor of 0.954 while the most negative impact is shown by Irritation with a impact factor of -0.542.

IX. LIMITATION

The most important limitation of the study is that the research was only focused on the Youths attitude towards Mobile-Advertising in general.

The collection of the data to conduct the study was collected using convenience sampling. So, the result of the study can be more accurate and optimized by including more samples in the data which can help in generalization of the result more effectively and efficiently.

Because the research was conducted by collecting data from the literates (University students), English was chosen as the medium of advertisement. The result would have been more generalized if the study of research had been conducted beyond the Universities campus. The research has been used to study the Attitude towards Mobile-advertising only for a section of people, i.e., Youths. If it may be conducted on all age groups of people then the result and analysis of the research study will be different and more generalized.

It can also be the case that the respondents may have provided us with unreliable data as they just don't want to fulfill the need to participate in the research. Another risk can be that the respondents may have perceived something else from the questions in the questionnaire but there actual sense was different.

X. CONCLUSION

The study achieved its primary goals by investigating the factors that influence Youths attitudes toward Mobile-advertising. This study tested five independent variables: entertainment, informativeness, credibility, irritation, and personalization. The findings of this study show that all of the independent variables influence youths' attitudes toward Mobile-advertising. As a result of all the analysis and findings, it can be said that all of the research questions and objectives have been met and answered.

The final results after performing the analysis of the study shows that the Youths of today have a positive attitude towards M-advertising or Mobile-advertising. Personalization has been found to be that most significant factor in case of youths in Mobile-advertising. The finding of the research/study can be used by various companies that are targeting youth to build their effective and efficient marketing plan or marketing mix. The study shows that the attitude of youth not only correlates with personalization but it also correlated with other variables as well. Overall, the research provided very useful information for future studies to conduct additional research on youths' attitudes toward Mobile-advertising.

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